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DEEP NIC

Mapping Nicosia's
urban centre
1960-2020

Business Activity
in the urban centre of Nicosia,
1960-2020: An overview

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INTRODUCTION

This overview is part of a larger research project called Deep Mapping Nicosia's urban centre, 1960-2020 (DeepNic) where we examine the transformation of the urban centre of Nicosia on three levels, namely, demography, business activity and monument building, in conjunction with key socio-political events occurred during this period and are described below, providing simultaneously the historical context of the project. It does not attempt to analyse in detail the technical aspects of economic development during this long period. This has already preoccupied the economists.¹ What follows is a description of our methodology and the challenges we encountered during our research on the business activity in Nicosia and a summary of our key observations and remarks. The project attempts to provide an insight into whether and to which extent the types and volume of business activity in the centre of Nicosia have been affected by certain key events happened since 1960, across the divide.

Cyprus's economic development and modernisation in its first years as an independent state, as well as in the aftermath of the 1974 war when the economy quickly reached its pre-war levels, was so rapid and intense that it has often been described as an economic miracle.² Is this reflected in the urban centre of Nicosia? To what extent has business activity in the urban centre of Nicosia is related to political developments within this 60-year period? Are there any fluctuations in the volume and type of business activity? These are some of the questions DeepNic will attempt to answer where data becomes available.

NOTES

- ¹ Indicative Sources: Andreas Theophanous, *Economic Miracle in Cyprus* (Nicosia: Intercollege Press, 1994); Andreas Theophanous, "The anatomy of the 'economic miracle', 1974-1994", in *The Anatomy of a Change: Cyprus After 1974*, eds. Nicos Peristianis and George Tsangaras (Nicosia: Intercollege Press, 1996); Clerides, Sofronis, "The Collapse of the Cypriot Banking System: A Bird's Eye View." *Cyprus Economic Policy Review* 8, no. 2 (2014): 3-35; Apostolides, Alexandre. "Beware of German gifts near elections: how Cyprus got here and why it is currently more out than in the Eurozone." *Capital Markets Law Journal* 8, no.3 (2013): 300-318
- ² Caesar V. Mavratsas, "Greek Cypriot Economic and Political Culture: The Effects of 1974." In *Cyprus and Its people: Nation, Identity, and Experience in an Unimaginable Community*, ed., Vangelis Kalotychos (Colorado: Westview Press, 1998); Oktay, Derya. "Domestic Politics in Cyprus: Grounds for Migrant Voices." *Journal of Mediterranean Studies* 17, no. 2 (2007):355-382

Information varied across the divide and as it was expected sources on the economy of the Republic of Cyprus were significantly easier to locate and in more detail. However, efforts were made to detect the fluctuations of the business activity in the Turkish Cypriot community, with the aim to document a more coherent picture for the city during these sixty years. Furthermore, an essential parameter to bear in mind in the analysis of the business activity in Nicosia is, inevitably, the fact that Nicosia has been divided in two since 1964 and even before then. In fact, in 1958, the British installed a barbed wire to divide the Greek from the Turkish sector of Nicosia, amid violent intercommunal clashes. In 1964, following an intercommunal violent incident and a political crisis, with the intervention of the United Nations, Nicosia was divided into a Greek and Turkish sector, by an UN-patrolled demarcation line, known, since March 1964, as the "Green Line". This line, or buffer zone, was consolidated and extended to the whole island after the war of 1974 and is still in force. The existence of a buffer zone for so long might have played a significant role in the volume and type of business activity in the city's centre because it implies, firstly, that a considerable piece of land in the middle of the city remained abandoned and unused. The loss of communication and interaction between the northern and southern parts of Nicosia inevitably increased mistrust and ignorance; the city was not developing as one area, but in two different paces depending on each part's human capital and resources. A representative example of this situation is the markets. For example, while Nicosia once was the most urbanized and multicultural place in the island, reflected in the presence of vendors and customers in the municipal markets, such as in Ermou street, the existence of the buffer zone relocated commercial activity elsewhere.

This overview tries to detect whether key political and socio-economic events that took place in Cyprus between the island's independence in 1960 and the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic at the beginning of 2020 correlate with or reflect the volume and type of business activity in the urban centre of Nicosia. The events that form this project timeline are: The establishment of the Republic in 1960; intercommunal strife 1963-1967; the 1974 war and subsequent division of the island; the Nicosia Master Plan, 1979; the unilateral proclamation of the regime in the areas north of the buffer zone in 1983; the granting of work permits by the Republic of Cyprus to third country nationals; the opening of the crossings in 2003; Cyprus's accession to the EU in 2004; the financial crisis of 2013 and the covid-19 pandemic. It should be clarified though that the repercussions of this last development could not be analysed within this project which chronologically extends up to 2020, as they have been so widespread and enduring that they merit a separate analysis.

BRIEF HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Cyprus has been under successive empires for centuries before becoming an independent country. As part of the Ottoman Empire for more than 300 years from 1571 until 1878, a significant Muslim community was living in the island, enjoying a privileged treatment compared to non-muslim populations. This disproportionate balance of power, rights and privileges existed between the two communities changed with the introduction of the British rule in 1878 and the restructuring of the justice system. However, the existence of two separate communities, each with a distinct ethnic identity, religion, language, and national orientation in what was supposed to be a British Colony continued and grew stronger. The end to the British rule came after an armed revolt carried out by EOKA³ during which intercommunal rivalry culminated with each community becoming more clinched on their national goals, i.e. *enosis* (union with Greece) for Greek Cypriots and *taksim* (division of the island into two parts) for Turkish Cypriots. On August 16, 1960, Cyprus became an independent state, after 82 years of British colonial rule. The island's independence was firstly agreed in Zurich in February 1959, between Great Britain, Greece, and Turkey. The Zürich Agreements were ratified a few days later in London by the representatives of the two communities, Archbishop Makarios on behalf of the Greek Cypriots and Dr Fazıl Küçük on behalf of the Turkish Cypriots. The establishment of the new Republic was accompanied with a Treaty of Guarantee, signed between the Republic of Cyprus and Greece, Turkey, and the United Kingdom. According to this Treaty, the guarantor powers pledged to recognize and guarantee the independence, territorial integrity and security of the Republic and they undertook to prohibit any activity promoting, directly or indirectly, either union of Cyprus with any other state or partition of the island.⁴ This aimed at preventing the repetition of actions aiming at *enosis* or *taksim*, but on the same time, three other countries were given a role and a saying over an independent and sovereign state something that partly explains, the continuing attachment of the two communities to their national centres.

President Makarios' attempts, in 1963, to amend certain provisions of the Constitution were rejected by Turkish Cypriots. This became the first of many disputed events in the early years of the Republic. While some saw Makarios' move as an attempt to prevent deadlock in decision making bodies, others perceived it as a deliberate effort to weaken the position of Turkish Cypriots in the government and to remove them from decision-making bodies. In December 1963, the killing of two Turkish Cypriots by a Greek Cypriot policeman in the walled city of Nicosia during patrol ignited violent intercommunal clashes that dragged into the first months of 1964, while after a short impasse, a new round of violence broke out again in 1967. In the aftermath of these

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- 3 EOKA stands for National Organisation of Cypriot fighters. It was a guerilla group led by Colonel George Grivas that fought towards overthrowing the British rule and achieving union of the island with Greece.
- 4 United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Island, Greece and Turkey and Cyprus, No.5475. *Treaty of Guarantee* signed 16 August 1960, United Nations -Treaty Series, p.2

events, Turkish Cypriots retreated into a series of enclaves, a move that was counteracted with a severe economic embargo. With the intervention of the United Nations, Nicosia was divided into a Greek and Turkish sector, by an UN-patrolled demarcation line, known, since March 1964, as the Green Line. As a result, Security Council Resolution 186 established the UNFICYP with a mandate to prevent a recurrence of fighting between the Greek and Turkish Cypriot communities.⁵ While the embargoes and restrictions to movement were lifted in 1968, Nicosia did not recover from the partition of the city. On the contrary, the participation of Nicosia was consolidated in 1974 and expanded throughout the island. Relations between the two communities never really improved, while the dictatorship in Greece and Turkey's expansionist aspirations resulted in a war that divided the island - a division that is still in force today. A coup d'état against President Makarios in July 1974, led by the Greek army officers stationed on the island, gave Turkey the pretext to invade the island based on the Article VI of The Treaty of Guarantee (1960) as justification to protect Turkish Cypriots who were under threat. Within a few days Cyprus was counting a heavy toll: hundreds of people died, or went missing, and thousands lost their houses and became refugees. The geographical division was soon followed by a demographic one; the Green Line was extended to the whole island, while a large Turkish military regiment was established in the northern part of Cyprus. In 1975, the voluntary regrouping of populations was agreed at the Vienna intercommunal talks, where the Turkish Cypriot population in the south moved to the north and Greek Cypriots to the south, creating two homogeneous zones divided by the UN controlled buffer zone.

Since 1974, significant steps have been made for confidence building and collaboration between the two communities, and the Nicosia Master Plan runs prominently among them. It was a daring collaborative initiative of Lellos Demetriades and Mustafa Akıncı with the aim to solve tangible and quotidian problems caused by unplanned development following the 1974 war and the division of the island. The plan remains in force until today, while bi-communal cooperation has been extended to several strata of the Cyprus society, i.e education⁶, culture, entrepreneurship and many more. In the meantime, many efforts had been taken place for the solution of the Cyprus problem, with the involvement of the international community, but none of them succeeded although in certain cases like in 1978, 2004 and 2017, negotiations made such progress that the solution seemed possible. In fact, in 1983, the Turkish Cypriot leadership unilaterally announced the establishment of the 'Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus' (15 November) which was declared illegal by the UN Security Council in resolution 541. Hitherto, 'TRNC' is only recognised by Turkey which continues to station approximately 35,000 troops in the island. After 1974, many Turkish Cypriots are said to have left their homes and workplaces in the centre

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- 5 The Security Council Report, Chronology of events, p11 <https://www.securitycouncilreport.org/chronology/cyprus.php?print=true>, Accessed 17.10.22
- 6 See the Association for Historical Dialogue and Research's "Imagine" Educational Program on Anti-racism Education/ Education for a Culture of Peace which was run between the years 2017-2022. The programme, which was implemented with the agreement of the leaders of the two communities on the island, reached 6117 students, accompanied by 714 teachers who were trained in the Imagine Project. Another 518 teachers were trained in Peace Education both mono-communally and bi-communally and another 92 head teachers participated in the 'Imagine' Head Teachers conference. For more information: <https://www.ahdr.info/peace-education/58-education-for-a-culture-of-peace-imagine>.

of Nicosia while Turkish nationals with different socio-cultural backgrounds and generally lower income levels, settled (were placed) in the vacant places.

Despite the Cyprus problem, on May 1, 2004, Cyprus became a full EU Member State, along with the other nine acceding countries. The accession of Cyprus into the Union inevitably had a significant impact on the economic development of the island, its demographic composition due to the influx of European citizens, and the government and administration of the country which had to adapt to EU laws and regulations. This event however, also created a further chasm across the divide, demographically, culturally, and financially, as the EU acquis is suspended in the northern part of the island. In 2008 the Republic of Cyprus joined the eurozone and adopted the Euro as its currency. Nine years later, 2013 made Cyprus a headline on the news around the world, when the Eurogroup and the recently inaugurated President of the Republic of Cyprus, Nicos Anastasiades, agreed to a rescue deal that would include the bail-in of uninsured and insured depositors in all Cypriot financial institutions. As experts claimed, the consequences were both direct and enduring. The haircut of deposits in the country's two largest banks was unprecedented in conception and scale and dealt a huge blow to the Cypriot economy. The crisis brought the economy of the Republic to its knees, while the Turkish Cypriot community is becoming increasingly financially dependent on and affected by the Turkish economy.

METHODOLOGY, LIMITATIONS AND DIFFICULTIES

Our main source of data was the Statistics Department of the Republic of Cyprus: Population Censuses, Annual Labour Reports, and the CY-STAT Database online. The Cyprus Chamber of Commerce and Industry only holds records of current business entities, which were out of the scope of this research, while limited archival records were kept by the Business and Professional Women Association (BPW). Information was also requested from the Municipality of Nicosia, which allowed access to a closed tax database. However, data differed for each case, i.e., for some establishments there was a time trajectory available, and conclusions could be drawn as to its use over the years; for others, information was only available from a certain year onwards and for others there was only information on the current situation. The Municipality's database is an excellent source of information about the evolution of the city centre, but it requires a massive amount of time for a researcher to go through all the establishments one by one, on every street, something that could not be completed during the timeframe of this project.

For the Turkish Cypriot community, the data available was not as extensive. For example, in relation to the labor force and unemployment, one of our main sources was the Household

Labor Force Survey, 2020 by the Statistical Institute of the Turkish Cypriot administration, which provided information for the period 2014-2020. Regarding the types and volume of active establishments for the Turkish Cypriot community in Nicosia, these were available for four years only, from 2017 until 2020. It should be added that the data that was consulted for the purposes of the project included mostly public information, that is documents and reports that were made available online as well as data analysed in secondary sources. This resulted from the agreed approach to formally request data from institutions established before the war and the subsequent division of the island. Another barrier to data was the issues encountered in the archival systems of local administrations consulted. While a significant amount of data was available at the Turkish Chamber of Commerce and Nicosia Turkish Municipality, these were often unorganised, not digitised or searchable by criteria (date, location) and partially unavailable due to privacy regulations.

Women's entrepreneurship was something we had aimed to explore within this project, but very limited to no specific data was available. To achieve this, door to door research is required and this could not be conducted within the timeframe of the project. However, the lack of data in this field pointed out a gap in record keeping on behalf of local authorities and businesses associations. Data on women's entrepreneurship could have been better organized and more easily accessible to the public. To fill in some gaps as to the types of business activities that existed in the city centre, especially before the 1980s, when information was rather limited, we conducted a few interviews with business-people who run businesses in the area or had knowledge of the sector. However, this is not an oral history project, and therefore, while the interviews provided interesting anecdotal information, these were not expanded within the scope of this research.

Another difficulty that we encountered during our research was the difference in the numerical figures for the same year. For example, Labour Statistics for 2009 stated a certain figure for unemployment for the year, while this figure was amended in the next edition of the Labour Statistics for 2010. According to the Statistics Service, data is constantly under review and therefore these discrepancies appear in every revision of the Tables. Additionally, data on Business Sectors, gender, unemployment, and business establishments were not available for Nicosia for the whole period. Detailed information on business sectors for each of the regions of Nicosia in the Republic of Cyprus becomes available from 2008 onwards, while for the Turkish Cypriot community this detailed information is only available for 2020. Again, older records were not available through public access and a more specific request was not made to local administrations to reach sources outside of publicly published data. Therefore, to enable comparisons between different time periods, we gathered data on employment and unemployment for the whole of the Republic. Otherwise, comparisons would have been possible only

for twelve years, between 2008 until 2020. Another limitation we encountered was the differentiation in the business sectors that occurred during this period. As it is stated in more detail in Annex 1, in 1960 eleven categories were listed in the Census, but only nine in the subsequent three censuses, while in the 2001 census the categories increased to thirteenth and in the 2011 census, to nineteen⁷.

Finally, the reader should bear in mind that the key events that determine our chronological framework have not affected the two communities equally and simultaneously.

MAIN FINDINGS

An overview

In 1960, the newly independent state was a rather underdeveloped society, mainly agricultural, although it moved progressively and this was soon reflected in several sectors of the economy, like tourism and commerce. In fact, economic development and modernization during this period were rapid and intense, to the extent that some spoke of an economic miracle, since by 1974 Cyprus managed to look more like a western advanced society rather than an underdeveloped one, while also successfully maintaining an unemployment rate below 3%.⁸ Progress and development were disrupted by the 1974 war. However, according to economists the Republic of Cyprus experienced a second economic miracle, since the economy returned to pre-war levels relatively quickly. This was certainly not the case for the areas that were not under the effective control of the Republic of Cyprus, (areas henceforth termed 'Turkish Cypriot administration'). Prior to the 1963 conflict, the gross domestic income of the Turkish Cypriot community consisted of 17.9%, while this percentage is recorded to show a sharp fall to 5.1% in 1964.⁹ The Turkish Cypriot community's retreat into enclaves and the barriers to accessing customs, ports and airspace between the years 1963-1974 is known to have largely contributed to the lack of growth in business activities.¹⁰ From this period onwards, the Turkish Cypriot community has almost fully been economically dependent on Turkish financial aid. It is noted that in 1968 the Gross Domestic Income levels shows an increase to 11.1% with the financial packages sent from Turkey (estimated as 2.4 billion TL).¹¹

The period 1961-1973 was characterized by rapid economic growth, with the average real GDP growth rate reaching 7.4% per year. The main social drivers were the expansion of manufacturing, tourism, and agriculture, while the construction sector also played an important role.¹² The 1974 war halted the remarkable course of the Cypriot economy, while most of the wealth-producing resources and capital investments remained in the areas not under the effective control of the Republic of Cyprus. In addition, the Republic of Cyprus lost control over the only modern international airport in Nicosia, causing a

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- 7** As of 2008, the NACE Rev2 categorization system for Business Sectors is applied.
- 8** Mavratsas, "Greek Cypriot economy", 1998: 286; Joseph P. Joseph, Cyprus: Economy and Business, 60 years 1960-2020, Volume II, (Nicosia: Nomisma Publishing Ltd, 2020), 46
- 9** Plümer, 2008: 20-22.
- 10** Akarsu, 2017: 106.
- 11** Plümer, 2008: 22.
- 12** Αθανάσιος Ορφανίδης και Γιώργος Συρίχας, *Κυπριακή Οικονομία: Ανασκόπηση, Προοπτικές, Προκλήσεις*, (Nicosia: Central Bank of Cyprus, 2012), 11

complete interruption of air connectivity between Cyprus and abroad. Control was also lost over the port of Famagusta, through which most of the country's goods transited. As a result of the war, unemployment skyrocketed to 10.0% in 1974 and 16.9% in 1975.¹³ In fact, the war resulted in a sharp reduction of the total workforce of the Republic of Cyprus, almost by a fifth, due to the movement of Turkish Cypriot workers to areas north of the buffer zone, as well as the emigration of many Greek Cypriots. Indeed, an important aspect of the policy followed in the period after the war was the encouragement of Cypriots to temporarily seek employment abroad. In 1977, 14700 Cypriots (7.3% of the economically active population) were working in countries such as Greece, Bulgaria, and the Arab countries. Since the mid-1960s especially, Turkish Cypriots have played a drastically diminished role, and since the mid-1970s they do not feature at all in the Cyprus statistics.¹⁴

Nicosia's urban centre was highly affected by the consequences of the war. Its proximity to the Buffer Zone discouraged many people from rebuilding their homes or businesses there. In the Greek Cypriot community, a heightened sense of fear and uncertainty led many entrepreneurs to move their businesses outside the city centre, while the establishment of house unit complexes for displaced Greek Cypriots in the suburbs, like Latsia, Strovolos, Lakatamia or Anthoupoli, led to the development of new business hubs outside the city centre.¹⁵ Lack of investment made the area unattractive to entrepreneurs, residents and tourists and therefore many shops remained closed for decades.¹⁶ In the 1990s, Archbishop Makarios Avenue and the adjacent streets were established as the commercial centre of the city south of the Buffer Zone. Well known enterprises like *Marks and Spencers*, *Bata*, *Costas Theodorou*, had already transferred their business there. However, in the beginning of the new century, things changed again with the establishment of shopping malls offering comfortable shopping experiences to families (Latsia-2007; Engomi-2007; Kokkinotrimithia-2018) drove people away from the urban centre of Nicosia. This is, however, a tendency that is observed throughout the world, for the acute traffic and lack of enough parking facilities (because of the increased people's capacity to buy cars and inadequate transportation system) combined with uncomfortable weather conditions or inadequate facilities for pedestrians, make shopping malls much more attractive.

Likewise, communities, including the Turkish Cypriot and Armenian communities, north of the dividing line of Nicosia abandoned their homes and business, causing "the physical, social, economic and cultural values [of the city] to be adversely affected."¹⁷ After 1974, very few Turkish Cypriots remained in the walled city of Nicosia, which had been an area where mostly immigrants stayed because the unsuitable or compromised state of some establishments allowed for very low rents; therefore it was not considered "safe for locals to wander around these areas

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- 13 Ορφανίδης & Συρίχας, *Κυπριακή Οικονομία*, 15
- 14 Demetrios Christodoulou, *Inside the Cyprus Miracle: The Labours of an Embattled Mini-Economy* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota, 1992), xlii
- 15 Interview, Antis Nathanael (Former Senior Officer at the Cyprus Chamber of Commerce and Industry). 2.03.2023
- 16 Interview with Elena Theodorou (co-owner of Costa Theodorou Ltd), 10.03.23. She said that her father closed his business in Trikoupi street for people were afraid to move further from Eleftheria Square and towards the walled city.
- 17 Akarsu, 2017: 106; Ozdemir, 2018: 45.

at night¹⁸. In 1995, the vacant shops and offices are declared to be 12.22% in the walled city. On the other hand, it was announced to be 25.3% in 2011¹⁹.

Based on the available information on active business establishments in Nicosia, during the decade between 1995 and 2005, some interesting observations can be drawn. Indicatively, we observe a decrease in the number of establishments in the Manufacturing, Construction, and Hotels and Restaurants sectors in 2005 compared to 2000 and 1995, whereas these sectors noted an increase between 1995 and 2005, which could be read in conjunction with the increase of unemployment in the areas under the effective control of the Republic of Cyprus, and in Nicosia in particular. In the Greek Cypriot community, in 2005, 19942 people were registered as unemployed, whereas in 2000 the number was 15354 and in 1995, 7900.²⁰

Active establishments in Nicosia, RoC			
	1995	2000	2005
Mining and quarrying	30	32	17
Manufacturing	3513	2946	2635
Electricity, Gas and Water supply	8	6	7
Construction	2366	2426	2169
Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles, motorcycles and personal and household goods.	8072	7864	7872
Hotels and Restaurants	1865	1895	1790
Transport, Storage and Communication	1272	1260	1250
Financial Intermediation	572	672	871
Real estate, renting and business activities	1467	1527	1735
Public administration and defense; Compulsory social security	347	344	346
Education	815	867	812
Health and Social Work	850	1062	1091
Other community, social and personal service activities	1999	2167	2182

Figure 1:
Active Establishments in Nicosia, 1995-2005.
Source: Census of establishments - volume i: number of establishments and employment by branch of economic activity - 2005

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¹⁸ Can, Atakara, 2021: 286.

¹⁹ Ozdemir, 2018: 46.

²⁰ Labour Statistics, Statistical Service of the Republic of Cyprus for the years 1996, 2002, 2006

Foreign labour force

In the aftermath of the 1974 war, in the areas under Turkish Cypriot administration, the labour force was enhanced by foreign nationals, predominantly Turkish citizens, to meet the needs that emerged after the division of the island. In February, 1975, under the "Regulation on Closing the Workforce Deficit in the Turkish Region of Cyprus with the Labor Force to be Sent from Turkey," a special agreement²¹ was signed between Turkey and the Turkish Cypriot administration to attract approximately 30,000 migrants from Turkey.²² The majority arrived to Cyprus between 1975 and 1977 from the regions around Trabzon (East Black Sea), Antalya, Mersin, Adana (Southern Turkey), Çarşamba, Samsun (West Black Sea), Konya (Central Anatolia) and southeastern Turkey. According to the Turkish Cypriot authorities, between 1974 and 1981, a total of 21,851 'citizenships' were offered to Turkish nationals, the largest part of which was to these early 'settlers' who arrived during the first couple of years.²³ Between 1975 and 2003, of the 53,000 persons who were declared eligible for 'citizenship', 45,689 were of Turkish-mainland origin; 4,650 were second- and third-generation Cypriot descendants born abroad, 1,094 were from Bulgaria, and 1,825 were from other countries.²⁴ In 2005, labour statistics of the Turkish Cypriot administration placed the number of registered mainland Turkish nationals working in Cyprus at 16,277. Most of these registered workers were employed in tourism (hotels, casinos, and restaurants), industry, banks, universities, and other sectors requiring skilled labour. In the immigrant labour force in privately-owned hotels, the percentage of Turkish nationals reached 90%, or 3500 out of the 4,000 immigrant workers.²⁵

In the areas controlled by the Republic of Cyprus, the number of foreign nationals has increased dramatically since 1990 due to a variety of reasons: new labour legislation, accession of the country to the European Union; immigration flows due to conflict and instability in neighbouring countries, as well as the Cyprus investment programme of 2016, through which the Cypriot citizenship was granted to high income earners and investors in exchange for the purchase of property in Cyprus worth at least €500,000.²⁶ However, around thirty years ago, a labour shortage in some branches of the economy such as the building trade, public works and the service industries led the trade unions and employers to sign an agreement whereby migrant workers may be called in.²⁷ According to a Council of Ministers' decision of March 15, 1990 "Permit of entry and Temporary employment" would be given to 1500 foreign nationals to work in certain sectors such as hotels, construction and clothing to cover for the deficit of 1700 work positions that was predicted for 1990.²⁸ Since then, the number of foreign workers in Cyprus followed an upward trend. In 1990, 6,718 were registered in Cyprus, while, by 2011 this number rose to 119,867. Most foreign workers are employed in Private Households, Hotels & Restaurants, Wholesale Trade and Retail, Construction and Manufacturing.

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- 21 The agreement brought workers (namely skilled in the fields of Livestock, Horticulture, Agriculture, Fishing and other) under the status of 'Tarım İşgücü Statülü Personel' [Agricultural Labor Status Personnel]. According to a study, the workers would earn the right to a retirement compensation fee after 10 to 15 years of labour and return to their homelands. The same study states that though some returned, many remained and were granted identity cards with the right to vote, as well as land (though without deeds). (Ahmet Gürkan Atay, 2010: 70).
- 22 Purkis, Kurtulus, 2013: 5. Gürdallı, Koldaş, 2017: 762 It is proposed that the 'settler' label be restricted to the subcategory of 'agricultural labour', whose migration to the island formed part of a deliberate settlement policy pursued by both Turkey and the Turkish-Cypriot authorities following the partition of the island in 1974 in Mete, Hatay, *Beyond Numbers: An Inquiry into the Political Integration of the Turkish 'Settlers' in Northern Cyprus* (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus centre, 2005), vii
- 23 Hatay, *Beyond Numbers*, 13
- 24 Hatay, *Beyond Numbers*, 13 and Appendix I: Citizenships Granted, 1974-2003
- 25 Hatay, *Beyond Numbers*, 2005, 8
- 26 According to the decisions of the Council of Ministers (of 13.09.2016 and the subsequent decision of 21.05.2018), non-Cypriot investors can acquire Cypriot citizenship by naturalization as well as a Cypriot passport for them and their families (with exception based on the Population Register Law of 2002 - 2017).
- 27 Alfons Cucó, *Report on the demographic structure of the Cypriot communities*, 27 April 1992, 17. Doc.6589,1403-23/4/92-4-E. Available online: <https://assembly.coe.int/nw/xml/XRef/X2H-Xref-ViewHTML.asp?FileID=6916&lang=EN>
- 28 Απόφαση Υπουργικού Συμβουλίου 15.03.1990, υπογεγραμμένη από τον Γραμματέα του Υπουργικού Συμβουλίου στις 23.3.90 κατόπιν πρότασης Αρ 175/90 με τίτλο «Παραχώρηση Άδειας για Προσωρινή Απασχόληση σε Αλλοδαπούς Εργαζόμενους», που κατατέθηκε από τους Υπουργούς Οικονομικών, Εσωτερικών και Εργασίας και Κοινωνικών Ασφαλίσεων.

Private households are, in fact, one of the main employers of foreign workers. According to the ANAD report for 2000-2003²⁹, within this three-year period, in the republic of Cyprus enterprises with foreign labour force noted an upward trend, increased from 14,484 in 2000 to 21,379 in 2003, especially in the tertiary sector due to an increase employment of foreign workers by private households.³⁰

Figure 2:
Foreign Workers in the Republic of Cyprus, 1990-2011.
 Source: Labour Statistics 1990-2011, Statistical Service, Republic of Cyprus

Percentage of enterprises with foreign personnel in RoC		
Sectors	2000	2003
Primary	82,9%	88,2%
Secondary	22,1%	28,6%
Tertiary	44,9%	55%

Figure 3:
Percentage of enterprises with foreign personnel in RoC.
 Source: Human Resource Development Authority of Cyprus Report, "Longitudinal Trends in Foreign Labour Employment by Cyprus Enterprises, 2000-2003, Research and Planning Directorate, HRDA, July, 2004

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- 29** Αρχή Ανάπτυξης Ανθρώπινου Δυναμικού Κύπρου, Διαχρονικές Τάσεις Απασχόλησης Ξένου εργατικού δυναμικού από τις επιχειρήσεις της Κύπρου, 2000-2003, Διεύθυνση Έρευνας και Προγραμματισμού, ΑνΑΔ, Ιούλιος, 2004 (Σύνοψη της μελέτης v-xix).
- 30** In the tertiary sector the increase is 49,9%, i.e. from 11.989 in 2000 it increase to 17.968 in 2003. ANAD, Διαχρονικές Τάσεις, 2004.

Proportionally, Nicosia ranked across all sectors, second to Paphos, with 53,07% and 60,4% foreign workers respectively in 2003. However, Nicosia ranked first in the tertiary sector, where the number of enterprises with foreign employees was 7,892 in 2003. In 2003, the sectors with the highest number of businesses employing foreign workers were Private Households (12,320 enterprises, accounting for 57.6% of the total), Trade and Repairs (2,063 companies, making up 9.6% of the total), Hotels and Restaurants (1,513 enterprises, constituting 7.1% of the total), Agriculture (1,416 enterprises, comprising 6.6% of the total), and Manufacturing (1,095 enterprises, representing 5.1% of the total). Together, these five sectors accounted for 86.0% of all businesses with foreign employees.³¹

Furthermore, when examining the employment trends of foreign workers over the past decade, it is evident that the household sector continues to be the primary destination for third-country workers, particularly women:

Year	Household Activities		Construction		Agriculture		Manufacturing		All sectors	
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
2008	269	15924	4041	147	1372	143	891	175	9268	20435
2009	227	16727	2452	221	722	48	563	203	7509	20983
2010	581	20911	2607	79	1510	1590	621	229	8674	25785
2011	566	22013	2327	145	1141	222	840	181	9162	27206
2012	665	21846	1851	42	474	93	586	155	8307	25843
2013	813	20913	1312	37	1179	240	548	120	7795	25713
2014	560	19109	1266	75	2611	306	741	501	8167	24095
2015	384	16973	1390	89	1982	109	436	188	8208	21786
2016	216	11594	2452	137	2356	91	214	148	9073	16911
2017	775	11524	2394	5	1486	372	284	357	10720	17405
2018	839	12442	3157	72	864	434	927	109	12398	17493
2019	738	13489	5417	186	1203	308	1169	201	15640	19364
2020	615	17783	6933	233	2344	896	1969	299	21610	23103

Figure 4:
Sectors that occupy the largest numbers of third-country workers.

Source: CYSTAT-DB, Employment by nationality, economic activity NACE (rev.2), and gender, Annual

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31 Op.cit.

A potential connection to consider is that the rising educational and professional qualifications of Cypriot women appear to align with the employment of foreign women from less developed countries in domestic roles. However, it is important to highlight that the working and living conditions for many foreign workers are inadequate and substandard. Based on the country report on Cyprus by the European Commission against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI), especially in the case of female domestic workers, adverse working conditions, isolation, and further labour abuses like sexual exploitation turn immigrant workers to a vulnerable group.³²

This sizable population of migrant labour employed in low-paid professions has moved in to occupy residential and commercial buildings in the area that has been abandoned and allowed to decay since 1974 through a lack of sustainable urban planning and long-term absence of investment in infrastructure. However, despite urban decay and decline in the city core, its potential for growth and development was first recognized by the Nicosia Master Plan (NMP). In 1977, on the initiative of Lellos Demetriades and Mustafa Akinci, leaders of the two municipal authorities of Nicosia, started a daring collaborative initiative with the aim to solve tangible and quotidian problems caused by unplanned development following the 1974 war and the division of the island, and contribute to the rehabilitation of areas of Nicosia severely affected by the war. They firstly agreed on the need of a common sewerage system and then in 1979, under the umbrella of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the leaders agreed to work, together with their technical teams, on the improvement of the existing and future habitat and human settlement conditions of the citizens of Nicosia. A bicomunal multidisciplinary team of national and international experts such as town planners, architects, civil engineers, sociologists, economists, etc. was formed in 1981 to prepare a joint Master Plan for the revitalization of several pilot areas in the walled city across the divide, i.e. Chrysaliniotissa, That-el-Kale and Arabahmed.³³ The Nicosia Master Plan remains in force until today and is in close collaboration with UNDP/USAID for several bi-communal rehabilitation projects. Gradually, the appearance and infrastructure of the city core improved and became more attractive to residents and young entrepreneurs. It could therefore be argued that the effects of the Nicosia Master Plan were positive on the revitalization of the city and substantial cooperation between the two communities.

The opening of the crossings

On 23 April 2003, Nicosia experienced historic moments when travel restrictions were eased and people were allowed to cross the dividing line for the first time since 1974. According to RoC Police data, 1.123,720 and 1.371,099 crossings took place from the Greek Cypriot and Turkish Cypriot community respectively.³⁴ This change enhanced urban rehabilitation aided by UN and EU

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- 32** The ECRI report is found in Deniz Sert, "Domestic Politics in Cyprus: Grounds for Migrant Voices." *Journal of Mediterranean Studies* 17, no. 2 (2007): 355-382
- 33** UNDP-UNCHS [HABITAT], *Nicosia Master Plan final report*, (Nicosia:1984)
- 34** David Jacobson, Bernard Musyck, Stelios Orphanides, Craig Webster, *The Opening of Ledra Sreet/Lozmaci Crossing in April 2008: Reactions from Citizens and Shopkeepers* (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre, 2009), 10

programmes proposed United Nations Plan for the reunification of the island (Annan Plan) by the Greek Cypriot community, optimism for possibility of solution and renewed interest by the international community to invest in the negotiations process continued for some years after.³⁵ The opening of crossings were, in fact, instrumental in facilitating interaction between the two communities, especially the opening of the Ledra Street/ Lokmaci crossing on 3 April 2008. Currently, there are nine open crossing points.

When the Ledra street crossing opened more than 97 thousand crossings were registered during the first month and 20,000 during the first weekend alone.³⁶ It was the only crossing that was in the heart of the commercial centre of the capital which, as David Jacobson and colleagues have acutely noted, "ceased to be yet another theatre of confrontation for the Cyprus problem but rather a link connecting the two communities".³⁷ To investigate the effects of the opening of the crossing on the business sector in the area, PRIO Cyprus run a survey with a target group of 51 Greek Cypriot and 50 Turkish Cypriot users of the Ledra street. The survey revealed that "the opening resulted in a win-win situation for Nicosia's old centre retail sector," as most businesspeople across the divide saw it as a positive development for their businesses, even if some establishments (like coffee shops or restaurants) benefited more than others, either with additional customers from both sides, or more tourists.³⁸ While Turkish Cypriots shopkeepers appeared more positive than their Greek Cypriots counterparts, both seemed to have experienced increasing revenues after the opening according to the survey. In fact, 39% of Greek Cypriot and 26% of the Turkish Cypriot participants in the PRIO survey said that they observed a 10% increase in their turnover.³⁹ Before this, PRIO Cyprus had compiled another report⁴⁰ to identify whether there were psychological barriers to intra-island commerce and to suggest practical steps to help address these barriers. The need for such report derived from two factors: the indications for comparatively low level of intra island trade, i.e. in goods equaled only 0.1% of Greek Cypriot and 7% of Turkish Cypriot trade with the rest of the world; and European Commission's reference in its 2007 report to psychological barriers to trade.⁴¹ The PRIO paper demonstrated that sales of goods across the Green Line had risen from just under EUR 475,000 in 2004 to EUR 4.9 million in 2007, while total transactions across the Green Line including shopping and casino spending amounted to an estimated EUR 31.7 million in 2007.⁴² However, it also stressed that when it comes to trade between the two communities, psychological barriers do exist and are reinforced by political leaders and the media; denial was the main psychological approach for Greek Cypriots and fear of being treated as inferior for Turkish Cypriots.⁴³

In 2010, Yorucu, Mehmet and Alpar published the results of another survey with a target group of 862 participants, during which they examined the effect of the opening of the Ledra

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- 35** On 24 April 2004 the proposed United Nations Plan for the reunification of the island, known as The Annan Settlement Plan, on uniting the island was subject to a twin-referendum. Turkish Cypriots voted in favour of the plan by 64.9% while Greek Cypriots voted against it 75.8%.
- 36** Jacobson et al, *The Opening of Ledra Street*, 10
- 37** Op.cit.
- 38** Op. cit. 20
- 39** Jacobson et al, *The Opening of Ledra Street*, 23
- 40** Mete Hatay, Fional Mullen, Julia Kalimeri, *Intra- Island trade in Cyprus: Obstacles, oppositions, and psychological barriers*, Paper 2/2008, (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre & British High Commission, 2008), 3. This overview will not deal with the volume, frequency, obstacles, types or other specific details of intra-island trade, as this falls outside its scope. A very good analysis of this is provided in the PRIO Paper.
- 41** Hatay et al, *Intra-island Trade*, 2
- 42** Hatay et al, *Intra-island Trade*, 1
- 43** Op.cit.

street/Lokmaci crossing on cross-border trade in comparison to the effect sustained by revitalization projects carried out by various aid agencies, i.e. EU, USAID, UNDP. The survey confirmed a major trade expansion in the shopping areas adjacent to the crossing in the SME sector. The results of the survey reveal that after opening the Ledra Street/Lokmaci checkpoint, 57.1% of the shopkeepers reported moderate (10% to 20%) increase in the number of tourist arrivals to the area north of the Buffer Zone from Ledra Street, while a further 27.5% reported significant (30% to 40%) increase, whereas only 6.6% reported better than 50% and another 8.8% reported more than 100% increase. The same respondents were asked to compare their income after the revitalization of the walled city coupled with the opening of Ledra/Lokmaci checkpoint. About 19.1% of the respondents indicated an increase, 49.5% claimed that there is no change, 17.2% reported a decline and 14.2% had no idea about their annual income.⁴⁴ Overall, the two reinforcing effects (i.e., revitalization projects and the trade liberalization after the opening of the crossings) seemed to have broadly similar quantitative trade creation impacts in the most directly affected business areas. In retrospect, earlier revitalization/ restoration works provided complementary positive effects on trade creation that occurred after April 2008.⁴⁵ Yorucu et al support that the opening of the Ledra/Lokmaci crossing reversed the decline of the walled city as more shoppers and tourists started visiting the area, and this increased interest seemed to have generated an investment interest in the vicinity of the area, resulted in cultural enrichment of the area and facilitated intra-island trade.⁴⁶ Focusing on whether particular types of businesses were more likely to experience increases in turnover following the opening, the vast majority of Greek Cypriot enterprises that benefited were optical shops, restaurants and “uncategorised shops”; among Turkish Cypriots, it was only restaurant owners who experienced increased turnover. Other categories in which a majority (just over 50 percent) of Greek Cypriots saw their sales increase were clothing, souvenir, and electronics shops. Categories in which a majority (over 50 percent) of Turkish Cypriots saw their sales increase included souvenir and clothing shops.⁴⁷

The opening of the Ledra Street crossing is not the first case of trade liberalization in Cyprus. Limited intra-island trade across the divide became legally possible on 23 August 2004 as the EU’s Green Line Regulation came into force. The GLR was part and parcel of the Cyprus accession to the EU on 1 May 2004.⁴⁸ Having mentioned this, it should be noted that the Cyprus’s accession to the European Union did not affect the two communities in the same way; the per capita gross domestic product (GDP) of the Republic of Cyprus reached \$23,735 in 2004, when it became a full member of the EU, while the part of the island under Turkish Cypriot administration lagged behind. Internationally isolated and subsidized heavily by Turkey, its per capita GDP was one-third that of the Republic of Cyprus at the time of EU accession.⁴⁹

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- 44** Vedat Yorucu, Ozay Mehmet, Resmiye Alpar & Pinar Ulucay, “Cross-Border Trade Liberalization: The Case of Lokmaci/ Ledra Gate in Divided Nicosia, Cyprus.” *European Planning Studies* 18, no.10 (2010): 1761
- 45** Yorucu et al, “Cross-Border Trade Liberalization”, 1760
- 46** Yorucu et al, “Cross-Border Trade Liberalization”, 1762
- 47** Jacobson et al, *The Opening of Ledra Street*, 24
- 48** The Green Line Regulation: The whole of Cyprus is part of the European Union. However, in the northern part of the island, where the Government of the Republic of Cyprus does not exercise effective control, EU legislation is suspended in line with Protocol 10 to the 2003 Act of Accession. Since 1974 the ceasefire line (referred to as the “Green Line”) has separated the two parts of the island. The line is not an external border of the EU. Council Regulation 866/2004 (“Green Line Regulation”) sets out the terms under which persons and goods can cross this line from the non-government-controlled areas into the government-controlled areas. https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/structural-reform-support/green-line-regulation_en
- 49** George. C. Georgiou, “Cyprus’s Financial Crisis and the Threat to the Euro”, *Mediterranean Quarterly* 24:3 (2013), 57, DOI 10.1215/10474552-2339462

Indeed, Turkey extends generous economic aid packages to the Turkish Cypriot community every year. In 2005, for instance, financial assistance from Turkey reached 217.2 million dollars, enough to finance most of the Turkish Cypriot administration's trade deficit.⁵⁰ By 2008 the per capita GDP had risen to \$29,400 in the Republic of Cyprus, while in the areas outside the effective control of the Republic of Cyprus, the figure remained approximately one third of that.⁵¹

Foreign trade by countries in northern Cyprus in selected years

Countries	1977		1985		1990		1995		2000		2005	
	Imp.	Exp.	Imp.	Exp.	Imp.	Exp.	Imp.	Exp.	Imp.	Exp.	Imp.	Exp.
Turkey	30.9	6.6	65.1	5.4	153.5	7.9	194.8	20.2	275.1	18.7	817.4	34.2
Other countries	51.1	17.3	77.9	40.9	228.0	57.6	171.3	47.1	149.8	31.7	438.1	33.9
EU countries	37.3	15.3	52.9	35.1	131.1	51.0	102.0	36.5	103.2	20.3	264.3	18.6
UK	20.8	11.8	27.5	31.2	67.1	44.0	49.4	23.8	43.3	18.8	101.4	13.8
Other EU countries	16.5	3.5	25.4	3.9	64.0	7.0	52.6	12.7	59.9	1.5	162.9	4.8
Middle East countries	3.4	1.2	0.8	4.5	6.4	1.6	8.1	1.6	7.5	3.9	42.0	6.8
Far East countries	5.1	—	10.7	—	52.3	—	33.5	—	14.1	—	52.0	—
USA	0.4	0.2	1.4	0.1	5.7	3.3	2.8	0.1	5.2	0.2	8.3	0.1
Other countries	4.9	0.6	12.1	1.2	32.5	1.7	24.9	8.9	19.8	7.3	71.1	8.4
Totals	82.0	23.9	143.0	46.3	381.5	65.5	366.1	67.3	424.9	50.4	1255.5	68.1

Note: Values are in 1977 millions of dollars.

Source: State Planning Organization (SPO) of Northern Cyprus, Statistical Yearbook of 2006.

Women in the workforce

We had intended to delve deeper into the contributions of women in the workforce and female entrepreneurship within the framework of this project. Unfortunately, the scarcity of comprehensive data spanning the entire period, particularly concerning the Turkish Cypriot community, limited our analysis to making observations primarily about the Greek Cypriot community. In the Turkish Cypriot community, there are two active civil society organisations that are run by and dedicated to activities of women in the workforce, these are the Business Women's Association and the Turkish Cypriot Women Entrepreneurs Association. There is also the Women Entrepreneurs Council under the Commerce Turkish Cypriot Chamber of Commerce. These associations and the council were established fairly recently, and while they are active in current events and in supporting women's visibility and place in the workforce, their missions do not necessarily include acting as repositories of archival materials on historical activities. This is neither the mission of Business and Professional Women's Association which is active in the Republic of Cyprus.

While in the 1960s there was a noticeable increase in the participation of women in the workforce and city life⁵², the 1974 war accelerated this trend. In the areas controlled by the Republic of Cyprus, women were called to fill so many positions created after the war to contribute to the economic development of their country, marking a significant turn in women's role in the

Figure 5:

Source: Ahmet Özyigit, *The Impact of Aid on the Economy of Northern Cyprus*, *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, Vol. 40, No.2 (May, 2008), 185

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⁵⁰ Ahmet Özyigit, "The Impact of Aid on the Economy of Northern Cyprus", *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, Vol. 40, No.2 (May, 2008), 186

⁵¹ Georgiou, "Cyprus's Financial Crisis", 58

⁵² Stavros Stavrou, "Cypriot Women at Work", *The Cyprus Review*, Vol.9 No.2 (1997), 60

society, and surely, a significant differentiation of the pre-1974 conditions when the role of urban women was largely confined to house-keeping and child-upbringing, or in sectors like agriculture or dressmaking, professions for which no advanced education was required. This changed after 1974 when women started acquiring new roles in the economy. Labour Reports of the Statistics Department of the Republic of Cyprus, show the striking increase of women in the gainfully employed population in the first twenty years after the war. In 1976, 81,500 men and 35,200 women belonged to waged labour, while in 1994, the figures rose to 163,800 and 106,200 respectively. This means that the 71,000 women, i.e. 38.4% of the total economically active population, entered the labour market between the two dates.⁵³ A glance at the statistics on the economically active population in the Republic of Cyprus, on the census years is indicative of the increased participation of women in the labour market, after 1974 (See Figure 6). During the 1980s, mobilization towards the elimination of inequalities between men and women in education and work led to a series of laws for equal pay, maternity leave, civil marriage and divorce, custody and guardianship of children, etc that significantly facilitated women's participation in the labour force and women's working conditions.⁵⁴

From 1999 until 2009, employment in Cyprus followed an upward trend, for both men and women, while unemployment fluctuated between 3 and 6% during this decade, with the lowest figure recorded in 2002 (3.3%) and the highest in 1999 (6%). Among women the percentage reached 8% that year, while for men it was 4.6%. Based on the RoC statistical data, in the 60-year period between 1960 and 2020, the number of women participating in the labour market increased dramatically, since from 80195 working women in 1960, this number surged to 195258 in 2020. Within the male population the increase was also significant but not as impressive, rising from 161628 to 222096 in the same period.

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⁵³ Stavrou, "Cypriot Women", 62

⁵⁴ Op.cit.

⁵⁵ Figures for 1960 derive from the business sectors categories as they appear on the census. For the following years figures match the Category "Gainfully employed population in Cyprus" as it appears in the Labour Statistics 1976, 1982, 1992, 2001, 2011 (Statistical Service of the Republic of Cyprus).

⁵⁶ The 1960 census makes a distinction between economically active and inactive population above the age of 15 years old while the following census make a distinction between gainfully employed population and total economically active population. Therefore, the figure for the total economically active population is the sum of the other two columns. No unemployment figures are provided.

Year	Men	Women	Unemployment	Unemployment in women	Total economically active population
1960 ⁵⁵	161628	80195	Not available	Not available	241823 ⁵⁶
1976	100455	58831	6830	3968	202904
1982	121502	80098	6445	2850	230300
1992	163100	107500	5200	2800	286800
2001	180900	127000	12842	8092	329900
2011	208753	186470	33951	15649	432165
2020	222096	195258	34291	16096	451645

Figure 6 :
Gainfully employed population
in Cyprus on census years.

Source: Censuses of the Republic of Cyprus,
Statistical Service

Figure 7:
Economically Active population of the RoC, 1960-2020.

Source: 1960 census, Labour Statistics, Statistical Service of the RoC, 1976-2008⁵⁷, Labour Force Survey, 1999-2021, CYSTAT-DB

Business activity in the city, 2008-2020 and the 2013 economic crisis in the RoC

The statistics service of the Republic of Cyprus has provided data on the types of business activity in the district and city of Nicosia and employment within each sector, for each area within the Municipality of Nicosia. Therefore, comparisons could be drawn between the different time periods and between sectors and areas. This 12-year period, however, was marked by the grave economic crisis the Republic of Cyprus endured in March 2013, the biggest since 1974.

The events of March 2013 in Cyprus made the headlines around the world. The Eurogroup and the recently inaugurated President of the Republic of Cyprus, Nicos Anastasiades, agreed to a rescue deal that would include the bail-in of uninsured and insured depositors in all Cypriot financial institutions. On 16 March 2013, an agreement was reached with the Anastasiades government on the amount of €10 billion. It was also decided to raise an additional €5.8% through a haircut on deposits in Cypriot banks. The haircut was set at 6.7% for deposits up to 100,000 and 9.9% for deposits over 100,000. The deal was rejected by the Cypriot parliament on 19 March 2013 with 36 votes against and 19 abstentions and one absence. On 25 March 2013, EU Finance

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57 Gainfully employed population: The full-time equivalent number of persons who work in or for the establishment including proprietors and working partners, unpaid family workers and persons on short-term or paid leave (such as sick leave, casual leave or paid vacation); persons in military service are excluded/ **Economically active population:** The total gainfully employed persons, Cypriots working in the British Bases, the unemployed and persons in military service. (Labour Statistics, RoC Statistical Service)

Ministers and the International Monetary Fund agreed on a new plan under which the deposits of Cypriot banks exceeding 100,000 were haircut and the Bank of Cyprus and Laiki Bank were merged. The haircut of deposits in the country's two largest banks was unprecedented in conception and scale and dealt a huge blow to the Cypriot economy.⁵⁸ As experts claimed, the consequences were both direct and enduring. Indeed, in the following year, a difficult process of shrinking and merging branches of the Co-operative Central Bank of Cyprus took place. In August 2018 the Co-operative Central Bank finally closed its doors and the Hellenic Bank undertook the employment of 1100 of its employees and the operation of its 72 branches around Cyprus.

The 2013 crisis and its consequences were reflected on Nicosia's business activity and employment, and in general women seem to become more affected (See annex 2).

Male employment in Nicosia, 2008-2020

Female employment in Nicosia, 2008-2020

Figures 8 and 9:
Male and Female employment
in Nicosia, 2008-2009.
Source: CY-STAT DB

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⁵⁸ Georgiou, "Cyprus's Financial Crisis"; Apostolides, "Beware of German gifts"

Remarks based on the 2008-2020 data on Nicosia

For the period 2008 until 2020, the Statistical Service of the Republic of Cyprus has provided detailed information on economic activity for each of the neighborhoods of the Municipality of Nicosia, not only for the whole of Nicosia, allowing us to make several comparisons, the most underlining of these could be the following:

- Between 2008 and 2009 there was a considerable increase in employment in the Hotel and Restaurants Sector in Nicosia. In 2008, 2941 men and 2971 women worked in the sector while the figures rose to 3502 and 3801 respectively in 2009. However, the urban centre did not seem to be much affected. In this sector, the number of establishments active in the urban centre rose to 474 in 2009, up only four from 2008, while in 2010, their number fell back to 466 and continued decreasing, reaching 456 in 2013. However, and despite the financial crisis of 2013, this number increased to 476 in 2014, with the majority of new establishments found in the areas outside the walled city, towards Pallouriotissa and Kaimakli.
- In the Trade category, there were 2949 active establishments in Nicosia, most of which (968) were located in the Trypiotis area which covers the main commercial streets of Nicosia , Agioi Omologites (469), Ayios Antonios (426), Panagia [Pallouriotissa] (323) and Kaimakli (302). By 2014, this number decreased to 2359. The areas mentioned sustained the most significant reduction, with the number of active establishments decreasing to 752, 390, 340, 272, 240 respectively. By 2020, the number of active establishments in the sector increased slightly, reaching 2403, but was unable to reach 2008 levels. There was some increase in the Trypiotis area (786), Agioi Omologites (424), and Kaimakli (260) but a further reduction in Agios Antonios (322) and in Panagia (269). In the area of Faneromeni, which includes the traditionally commercial roads of Ledras and Onasagorou, the active establishments were reduced from 101 in 2008, to 78 in 2014 and 66 in 2020.
- The Manufacturing sector also seemed to be decaying in Nicosia, since the active establishments reduced to 480 in 2020 from 726 in 2008. The reduction was significant in all areas of Nicosia, especially in Trypiotis (57, down from 74) and Agios Anotonios (from 67 to 41). In the neighbourhoods in the walled city this became very obvious: for example in Faneromeni (from 18 to 12), in Agios Savvas (from 33 to 18) in Omerye (from 36 to 15) in Agios Ioannis (from 14 to 5) un Tahtekale (from 43 to 20).
- However, it seems that Nicosia, in the last decade or so, found a new role in providing financial, professional scientific and technical services. In fact, financial services surged to 877 in 2020 from 419 in 2008 and flourished especially in the areas of Trypiotis (355 in 2020) and Agioi Omologites (270 in 2020). Another sector that marked a significant increase was that of Administrative and Support Service Activities (252

establishments in 2008 became 432 in 2020) and Professional Scientific and Technical Activities (1389 in 2008 and 2240 in 2020).

- Another sector which expanded was that of education since educational establishments increased from 203 in 2008 to 342 in 2020 in this area.

The diagrams below show the business sectors with the lowest number of active establishments in 2008 and how they evolved in 2004 and 2020, as well as the business sectors with the highest number of active establishments in 2008, 2014 and 2020⁵⁹.

SECTORS WITH THE LOWEST NUMBER OF ACTIVE ESTABLISHMENTS 2008,2014, 2020

Figure 10 & 11:
Sectors with the lowest and highest number of active establishments in Nicosia

Source: Active Establishments in Nicosia 2008-2011, CYSTAT-DB, Statistical Service of the Republic of Cyprus

SECTORS WITH THE HIGHEST NUMBER OF ACTIVE ESTABLISHMENTS 2008, 2014, 2020

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⁵⁹ Agriculture and mining which score very low in the urban centre, as well as water supply, electricity, and gas for which the market is limited were excluded from the calculation.

An interesting case of an area very close to the centre of Nicosia that attracts these types of business activity. Agioi Omologites, is an area south of the buffer zone, outside the walled town, but can be considered as part of the urban and commercial city as it attracts much business activity, especially in the financial and real estate sectors.

Figure 12&13:
Active establishments in the area of Agioi Omologites, 2008 and 2011.
 Source: Active Establishments in Nicosia 2008-2011, CYSTAT-DB, Statistical Service of the Republic of Cyprus.

With regards to the Turkish Cypriot community, little information was found for the period 2008 - 2020. According to the 2014 reports of the Statistical Institute of the Turkish Cypriot administration the total number of unemployed was estimated at 9320, i.e. the rate of unemployment was 8.3%.⁶⁰ In 2020 the total number of unemployed was 14950 people and the unemployment rate was 10.1%; 9.0% for men and for women it was estimated between 12.2%. and 16.3%. In addition, the unemployment rate of the young population in the 15-24 age group was calculated as 29.3%.⁶¹

The table below shows the active establishments per sector in the areas of Nicosia under Turkish Cypriot administration, between 2017-2020:

NACE	Sector	2017	2018	2019	2020
B	Mining and Quarrying	24	18	20	13
C	Manufacturing	866	852	854	690
D	Electricity, Gas, Steam and Air Conditioning supply	4	23	22	14
E	Water Supply; Sewerage, waste Management and Remediation Activities	45	41	40	29
F	Construction	639	741	768	821
G	Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motors and Motorcycles	3629	3935	3939	3107
H	Transportation and Storage	281	345	315	342
I	Accommodation and Food Service Activities	901	921	966	940
J	Information and Communication	164	159	190	135
K	Financial and Insurance Activities	554	736	1039	471
L	Real Estate Activities				
M	Professional Scientific and Technical Activities	992	1051	1068	1206
N	Administrative and Support Service Activities	175	195	230	212
O	Public Administration and Defence; Compulsory Social Security				
P	Education	139	150	164	177
Q	Human Health and Social Work Activities	401	420	424	453
R	Arts, Entertainment and Recreation	95	98	104	71
S	Other Service Activities	593	714	643	537

Source: <http://tarim.gov.ct.tr/%C4%B0statistikler>

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⁶⁰ HIA 2014, 5 İstatistik Kurumu, 2020 Hanehalkı İşgücü Anketi (Statistical Institute, 2020 Household Labor Force Survey)

⁶¹ HIA, 2020, 4

Concluding comment

On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared COVID-19, the disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2, a pandemic, following a rising spread of a potentially lethal virus. The world was alarmed. Countries sealed borders, schools closed, people started wearing masks and practicing "social distancing". A few days before the WHO announcement, the leaders of the two communities in Cyprus and the members of the Technical Committee on Health had met to discuss how to deal with this unexpected eruption of the pandemic. Despite the fact that hitherto Cyprus had not yet reported any Covid-10 cases, the Minister of Health announced the closing of four of the crossings. They remained closed for 15 months. Further research is required as to the effects of the pandemic on business activity in the urban centre of Nicosia.

Disclaimer: CYENS Centre of Excellence is a research and innovation centre that operates under the motto “Inspired by Humans Designed for Humans”. Its vision is to produce world-class research that drives innovation towards a social and economic benefit, while conducting excellent, internationally competitive scientific research in the areas of visual sciences, human factors and design, communication, and artificial intelligence. It is supported by the European Commission, the Republic of Cyprus and its founding partners: the Municipality of Nicosia, the Max Planck Institute for Informatics (MPI), University College London, the University of Cyprus, the Cyprus University of Technology, and the Open University of Cyprus. DeepNic is a research project, hosted by CYENS and funded by the Research Promotion Foundation. In conjunction with key socio-political events that occurred between 1960 and 2020, it investigates the evolution and transformation of Nicosia’s urban centre in three thematic areas: demography, business activity and monument building. DeepNic’s research team includes both Greek Cypriots and Turkish Cypriots and primary research was conducted across the Green Line. The project acknowledges the suffering that the people of the island have experienced during the island’s recent history and that terminology related to the conflicts between the Greek and Turkish Cypriot communities can be politically charged. CYENS aims to be objective and to use scientific inquiry as a tool that transcends political and social differences. Taking all this into consideration, CYENS’ decision for any publications derived from the DeepNic project is to use language that is as inclusive and respectful towards as many sensibilities as possible, with multiperspectivity and critical thinking as guiding principles, and to present DeepNic’s research results objectively, without any intention to offend or alienate. With this project, CYENS does not, in any way, afford any entities recognition that has not been granted by law.

Notes:

- The term “TRNC” is only mentioned in the text when data are copied out from the Censuses conducted by the statistical service of the Turkish Cypriot administration. This is done for accuracy purposes only and does not imply recognition of the illegal regime.
- The words *citizen* and *citizenship* are put in inverted commas when it is used for the population north of the buffer zone for the regime is not internationally recognized.
- The production of this overview would not have been possible without Thomas Nikidiotis, who helped with the documentation of numerical data from the RoC Statistics Department and Iliana Koulafeti and Loizos Kapsalis for their valuable feedback and cross checking.
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ANNEX 1

Table 1. Republic of Cyprus Sectors of the Economy data (from Censuses)

Censuses were conducted in 1960, 1976, 1982, 1992, 2001, 2011 and the last one in 2021. Based on the information we received from the Censuses, business activity was divided in the following categories, for which we have information with regards to locality and gender:

Census Year	Business Sectors
1960	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agriculture 2. Forestry 3. Fishing 4. Transport & Communication 5. Mining and Quarrying 6. Manufacturing 7. Construction 8. Wholesale & Retail trade 9. Government and Communal Institutions 10. Military Authorities 11. Entertainment and Recreation
1976, 1982, 1992	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing 2. Mining and Quarrying 3. Manufacturing 4. Electricity, Gas, Water 5. Construction 6. Wholesale & Retail trade (and, as of 1983 the category includes restaurants and hotels) 7. Banking/Finance, insurance and real estate 8. Transport, storage and communication 9. Community, social and Personal services
2001	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing 2. Mining and Quarrying 3. Manufacturing 4. Electricity, Gas, Water 5. Construction 6. Wholesale & Retail trade 7. Restaurants and Hotels 8. Transport, Storage and communication 9. Finance, Insurance 10. Real estate activities 11. Public administration and defense; 12. Education 13. Health and Social Work
2011 (NACE Rev.2)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing - A 2. Mining and quarrying - B 3. Manufacturing - C 4. Electricity, Gas, Steam and Airconditioning Supply - D 5. Water supply, Sewerage, Waste Management and Remediation activities - E 6. Construction - F 7. Wholesale and retail trade - G 8. Transportation and storage - H 9. Accommodation and Food Service activities - I 10. Information and Communication - J 11. Financial and Insurance activities - K 12. Real Estate activities - L 13. Professional and Scientific Technical Activities - M 14. Administrative and Support Service activities - N 15. Public Administration and defence; Compulsory social security - O 16. Education - P 17. Human health and Social Work activities - Q 18. Arts, Entertainment and Recreation - R 19. Other community, social and personal activities - S

ANNEX2

Employment in the RoC (total and Nicosia), 1999 -2020

Year	Cyprus			Nicosia		
	Total	Women	Men	Total	Women	Men
1999	296978	122934	174044	117881	50150	67731
2000	309093	131745	177348	122278	53769	68959
2001	322351	141424	180927	125634	58363	67272
2002	326075	144585	181489	130083	59600	70483
2003	341203	152470	188733	133968	61839	72129
2004	354686	156899	197787	138868	63614	75254
2005	367524	161129	206395	145963	65669	80294
2006	374485	165882	208403	153633	70551	83083
2007	393377	176572	216805	157452	73434	84018
2008	397374	178191	219184	158345	73462	84883
2009	404622	188655	215967	158229	76715	81514
2010	421628	199252	222377	162160	79394	82766
2011	432165	205022	227143	160830	79742	81088
2012	436742	206544	230198	158802	78523	80279
2013	433949	206143	227806	155160	78079	77081
2014	432288	209120	223168	150239	77214	73025
2015	420961	204805	216156	140362	71612	68749
2016	417069	201467	215602	146377	72470	73907
2017	426789	205006	221782	152385	74939	77446
2018	437495	208985	228509	160555	78294	82261
2019	448181	212157	236024	167499	80474	87025
2020	451645	211354	240191	168286	81470	86816

Labour Force Survey - Main Results by Gender, Annual by INDEX, MEASURE, GENDER and YEAR, Statistical service, RoC & Employment by Place of Residence, Economic Activity NACE (Rev. 2) and Gender, Annual

Unemployment 15+ in Cyprus and in Nicosia

Year	Cyprus				Nicosia
	Total	Women	Men	%	Total
1999	17718	9783	7936	6	
2000	15354	9657	5697	5	
2001	12842	8092	4750	4	
2002	10756	6030	4726	3.3	
2003	14109	6983	7127	4.1	4571
2004	16685	9724	6961	4.7	4749
2005	19492	10445	9048	5.3	5160
2006	17004	8960	8044	4.5	5255
2007	15428	8080	7348	3.9	4683
2008	14523	7557	6966	3.7	4268
2009	21704	10316	11387	5.4	5596
2010	26406	12782	13624	6.3	7180
2011	33951	15649	18302	7.9	8894
2012	51515	22828	28687	11.8	11992
2013	68871	31249	37622	15.9	16066
2014	69547	31501	38045	16.1	15914
2015	62758	30254	32505	14.9	13825
2016	54010	28831	27179	12.9	12135
2017	47166	23087	24079	11.1	10680
2018	36617	18270	18347	8.4	8598
2019	31703	16932	14770	7.1	7136
2020	34291	16096	18196	7.6	8059

Sources:

Registered Unemployed by District, Annual, Statistical Service of Cyprus, CYSTAT-DB

Figures for 1999-2002 for Nicosia are not available per district.

Figures for unemployment per gender per district, are not available.

